

Influence of Digital Marketing on Consumer Purchase Behavior

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ABSTRACT

Digital marketing is a marketing method to promote products in online. Digital Marketing industry in India is spread to almost all the business sectors. The power of digital marketing allows geophysical barriers to disappear making all consumers and businesses on earth potential customers and suppliers. It is known for its ability to allow business to communicate and form a transaction anywhere and anytime. Apart from that, it too lays down the impact on the mind of the customer so as to purchase the product. The purpose of study is to recognize the effectiveness and the impact of digital marketing in the buying behavior of consumers. For the data collection, Primary data is used. A structured questionnaire is used to collect primary data and the sample size is 50 respondents. The findings of the study reveals that the customer is aware of the digital media and more likely uses the digital channel for shopping goods. This study conducted in chengannur taluk in Pathanamthitta District.

KEY WORDS: *Digital Marketing, Customer Buying Behaviour, Consumer awareness, Chengannur Taluk*

INTRODUCTION

Today's time of Internet has opened the gateway of tremendous digital marketing opportunities for businesses. By utilizing different channels of digital marketing, businesses cannot just share their product and services online; additionally they can gain clients for their business, entice them and can convert them to boost their ROI. The world is super-connected nowadays and all things considered, marketing and advertising are no more the same as they once were. This is particularly valid because of the ascent of online networking, which has changed how organizations speak with potential and existing customers.

Digital market helps corporate to reach target customer via different channels like E- marketing, E-commerce, social media, websites, interactive marketing. Marketer can conducted online survey so as to get the required information from customer and analyse the response and correspondingly take action based on response of customers to meet their needs.

Digital Marketing is new form of marketing and opportunities for enterprise to communicate the potential customers. Digital marketing campaigns are becoming more prevalent as well as efficient, as digital platforms are increasingly incorporated into marketing plans and everyday life, and as people use digital devices instead of going to physical shops.

With the emergence of digital marketing, it is not an easy task anymore to woo the consumers.. To match the consumer-set standards, every brand has to make sure to be on their toes and everyone has maintained its presence on the social media platforms. Era has changed and so the mindset of the consumers. Consumers are now welcoming new products with fresh and good quality features with applause.

With so many options available in the market, it becomes difficult for the consumers to become loyal and switching becomes easy. It is the consumers that decide which social media platform the brand must use to expand its business. If the mass consumers are on Facebook, Snapchat, Twitter, Instagram, LinkedIn etc., it becomes mandatory for the brands to have their presence on these platforms if they want to be close to their prospects and a step ahead of their competitors, by interacting with their consumers and creating a buzz of their brand among them.

Objectives of the Study

- To recognize the effectiveness of digital marketing among consumers.
- To study the impact of digital marketing on consumer buying behavior.

them make the choice to engage you, instead of you going after them.

1. Consumers want relevant, engaging, and newsworthy content on demand. This means they expect to receive news about your industry as soon as it occurs, statistics about your industry, and other relevant information as it emerges. Internet marketing ensures consumers can find what they need to stay up-to-date. .
2. The Internet offers consumers a greater variety and choice than they've ever had before. In this way, Internet marketing is a huge benefit to consumers on a global scale.
3. Consumers can find information about your business at any time of the day. This effectively gives them unlimited access to the brand, allowing to engage potential consumers ie Digital marketing provides 24/7 access
4. Internet marketing gives you a chance to reduce paper as more marketing campaigns shift to digital, Marketers can work from anywhere, cutting down on fossil fuel use, Online shoppers don't need to drive to stores to find what they want.

Methodology Applied

Primary Data : The research is done through observation and collection of data through structured questionnaires from 50 respondents.

Secondary Data : Secondary data is collected from newspapers, journals, books and magazines to develop the theory.

Sample Size : For this study, the sample size 50 was taken for analysis.

How does Internet marketing benefit consumers

While increased visibility and access is definitely good for your business, Internet marketing also benefits your customers. Internet marketing is a way to lead consumers honestly toward your product or service based on their criteria. Presenting them with the right, useful information at the correct time lets

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Question	Category	No of respondents	% of respondents
Gender	Male	30	60
	Female	20	40
	Total	50	100
Age	Below20	10	20
	21-30	15	30
	31-40	14	28
	41 above	11	22
	Total	50	100
Qualification	Under graduate	12	24
	Graduate	20	40
	Post graduate	18	36
	Total	50	100
Occupation	Students	8	16
	Housewife	11	22
	Govt employees	9	18
	Business people	10	20
	Private employees	12	24
	Total	50	100
Monthly income	Below 10000	8	16
	10001-20000	12	24
	20001-30000	10	20
	30001-40000	11	22

	Above40000	9	18
	Total	50	100
Awareness of digital shopping	Having knowledge about digital marketing	42	84
	Not Having knowledge about digital marketing	8	16
	Total	50	100
Which of the digital channel do you aware of	Emails	6	14
	Social media	10	24
	Website	13	31
	Multimedia ads	8	19
	Others	5	12
	Total	42	100
Which digital channel influence you more to buy	Emails	4	10
	Social media	14	33
	Website	15	36
	Multimedia ads	4	10
	Others	5	11
	Total	42	100
What kind of product you prefer to buy	Convenience goods	10	24
	Speciality goods	7	16
	Shopping goods	25	60
	Total	42	100
Reasons for choosing digital shopping	Low price	8	19
	Variety of products	10	24
	Various payment mode	9	21
	Easy buying procedure	12	29
	Others	3	7
	Total	42	100
Frequency of purchasing	Once in a year	5	12
	2-5 times	7	17
	6-10	22	52
	11 and above	8	19
	Total	42	100
Problems that faced when you use digital channels for shopping	Security issues	11	26
	Payment failures	6	15
	Authenticity	9	21
	Additional charges	7	17
	Quality issues	9	21
	Total	42	100

- Ratio of male customers is very high in online shopping that is 60%
- Awareness about digital shopping is 84% among the respondents
- Income of respondents mainly falls in the range of Rs.10001-20000ie 24%
- Private employees are purchasing more than others through online shopping that is 24%.
- Most numbers of respondents that is 29% feels that online shopping have simple buying procedures.
- 52% of the respondents purchase the products 6 to 10 times annually.
- Majority of the respondents were influenced to buy more products through websites
- 60% of the respondents prefer to buy shopping goods through digital channels

- The major problem faced by the respondents were the security issues ie26%
- Overall the respondents are satisfied through purchasing digital marketing.

Conclusion

Digital marketing is about utilizing digital technology to achieve marketing objectives. There is no essential need for digital marketing to always be separate from the marketing department as a whole, as the objectives of both are the same. However, for now, it remains a useful term because digital marketing requires a certain skill set to utilize the digital technology effectively.

At the present time, still for tiny business proprietor at hand have an extremely inexpensive and competent method by using digital marketing to market their products or services in the society. It has no restrictions. Company can utilize any devices such as tablets, smart phones, TV, laptops, media, social media, e-mail and lot other to support company and its products and services. Digital marketing may achieve more if it considers high priority.

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